

Thermal and FTIR Studies of a New Tetramethylammonium(I)-exchanged 13X Zeolite

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Many zeolites are known with alkylammonium and other nitrogenous bases as the main cations in them. A high purity of TMA(I) counterpart of zeolite X was prepared in 5 days from a reaction mixture of composition $4.2\text{TMA}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{SiO}_2 \cdot 210\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with $(\text{R}_4\text{N})_2\text{O}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 = 1.5$ and 190 moles of water¹. This author had reported the adsorption behaviour of a TMA(I)-exchanged indigenous adsorbent hydrophilite for adsorbates like gaseous H_2S and CO_2 and aqueous NH_3 . In the present study, a TMA(I)-exchanged form of synthetic 13X zeolite has been prepared and its thermal and FTIR characteristics have been determined to ascertain the changes in the properties of the original X zeolite and compare these characteristics with other similar zeolite forms containing organic bases.

Results and Discussion

Of the four steps of weight-losses recorded on TG analysis (Table 1), the major step is found to be between 31.0 and 301.0^o with a loss of 23.97% which is about 87% of the total weight-loss recorded upto 700^o. The last step weight-loss between 330.0 and 492.0^o (2.62%) is another event worthnoting, although it proceeds at the lowest rate of loss. The second and third steps over a mere 5^o temperature range show negligible weight-losses. The peak temperatures recorded in DTG studies for the first and the fourth steps are 173.0. and 373.0^o respectively, with intermediate minor events at 322.0 and 327.0^o. DSC studies, however, provide only two peaks at 190.8 and 408.1^o with endothermic peaks for the corresponding first and fourth steps of weight-losses observed in TG data. The thermal behaviour can be described to be dehydration at the lower temperature limit upto 300^o and loss of TMA(I) above 300^o. Thermal behaviour observed with other TMA(I)-containing zeolites like Omega, N-A and Offretite indicated loss of TMA above 400, 300 and 350^o respectively^{3,4}.

On the basis of the composition of 13X, $\text{Na}_{86}[(\text{AlO}_2)_{86}(\text{SiO}_2)_{106}].264\text{H}_2\text{O}$, it contains 25.1% alumina. From the 2.60% TMA(I) observed on TG analysis of the new exchanged form as weight-loss above 330^o, ca. 5.80% $(\text{TMA})_2\text{O}$ is expected. This gives a value for $(\text{R}_4\text{N})_2\text{O}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ as about 0.23 assuming that no change in the alumina content occurs on cation exchange. Similarly on the basis of a 26.1% dehydration loss for 264 moles of water in 13X, 23.97% weight-loss upto 300^o for the TMA(I)-13X should correspond to about 242 moles of water. However, these values are only approximate as the actual composition weight of the exchanged form has not been considered. But these values indicate a possible alteration as a result of the introduction of TMA(I) ion in place of Na(I) in 13X.

FTIR spectrum of the exchanged form shows 37 peaks with weak to strong intensity between 3 500 and 450 cm^{-1} . Of these characteristic intense peaks for zeolite framework structure are evident at 1 020 and 970 cm^{-1} for asymmetric stretch, at 751 and 680 cm^{-1} for symmetric stretch, at 562 cm^{-1} for double rings and at 464 cm^{-1} for T-O bend (T = aluminosilicate tetrahedra). Fairly intense peaks at 3 441 cm^{-1} for low frequency hydrogen bonded OH groups and at 1 643 cm^{-1} for H_2O are also observed. Other notable peaks are found for N-H bending (1 525), C-H bending (1 472), N- CH_2 (2 822-2 774), C-H stretch (2 984-2 864) and N-H stretch (3 320-3 140 cm^{-1}). The last three groups of peaks are of very weak intensity⁵. The presence of the TMA(I) cation in the exchanged form is thus confirmed from its typical FTIR and thermal data, especially when compared with similar data obtained for 13X zeolite⁶. It is also seen that the framework structure of the original 13X zeolite remains unchanged in the new exchanged form.

Experimental

A saturated solution of tetramethylammonium(I) iodide (SISCO chemicals) was prepared in hot distilled water and the solution interacted with 13X zeolite sample in white powder form obtained from Indian Petrochemicals Ltd. The solution of the mixture was heated from time to time with constant stirring and after 10 days of contact, the solid was filtered, washed with hot distilled water and air-dried. A part of this exchanged sample was used to record its TG,

TABLE 1-THERMAL DATA (TG, DTG)

Sample wt mg	Wt loss (Temp range, ^o C)	Total wt loss, %	Rate of wt loss, %min ⁻¹	Peak temp ^o C
	23.97 (31.0-301.0)		1.776 0	173.0
	0.1037 (320.0-325.0)	27.56	0.414 6	322.0
21.23	0.1037 (325.0-330.0)		0.414 6	327.0
	2.620 (330.0-492.0)		0.324 0	373.0

DTG and DSC data on a Mettler TA3000 system in static air. From the percentage loss of weight over various temperature ranges at the rate of heating 20 K min^{-1} , rates of weight-losses were evaluated. Another part was used for FTIR studies in KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer 1800 spectrophotometer.

TABLE 2-THERMAL DATA (DSC)

Sample wt., mg	Temp. range	ΔH Endo mJ	ΔH J/G	Peak temp., °C
	25.0-380.0	2 5605	1 939.3	190.8
13.203	378.0-480 0	2 087.9	1 58.14	408 1

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